
URANIUM ORE DEPOSITS IN NORTHEASTERN NIGERIA: GEOLOGY AND PROSPECT

Saleh I. Bute

Department of Geology, Gombe State University, P.M.B 127, Gombe

ABSTRACT

Uranium potential in northeastern Nigeria occurs in sandstone-hosted and vein-type mineralization. Sandstone-hosted deposits occurs in sedimentary/volcanosedimentary sequences in structurally controlled Bima sandstone (B₂, B₃) at Zona and Dali, while the vein-type mineralization occurs in the deformed migmatites and granitoids at Gubrunde, Kanawa, Ghumchi, Mika and Monkin-Maza deposits. Sandstone deposits have been drilled by Nigeria uranium mining company (NUMCO) and seems to be elusive, which leads to its failure to search for economic deposits, the possible economic deposits is the vein-type.

KEYWORDS: Sandstone-hosted, Vein-type, Uranium, Gubrunde, Mika

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Corresponding Author Email:

INTRODUCTION

Mineral are naturally occurring inorganic, usually solid chemical elements or compounds that have fixed or well defined physical and chemical properties, uranium is not exceptional. An unusually significant or abnormal concentration of mineral in a place is called a mineral occurrence, when such an occurrence can be extracted profitably is known as mineral deposits, and if it contains useful materials and can be exploited profitably in the prevailing technical and economic environment is known as reserve(Ogezi, 2006).

Nigerian uranium ores are found in sedimentary sequences, Younger Granite Complexes and deformed basement rocks with granitoid composition, most are small and scattered (Fumilayo and Saleh, 2009). The common ores found are pyrochlore, monazite, Xenotime, uraninite, pitchblende, coffinite and autinite.(Fumilayo and Saleh,2009; Dada and Suh, 2006)..

The uranium potential in the northeastern part of Nigeria are the major deposits so far prospected. The mineralizations are Guburende, Kanawa, Zona, Dali, Mika, and Monkin-Manza and were all discovered by Nigeria uranium mining company (NUMCO), (Suh and Dada, 1998; Dada and Suh, 2006). This present work attempts to review and suggest possible procedures in finding economic uranium deposits in the area.

Table 1. 2004 Uranium production and number of active production centers by deposit type. (IAEA, 2009).

Deposit Type	%of 2004 production	Number of production centers
Unconformity related	39.3	4
Sandstone	28.6	20
Metasomatic	10.2	3
Haematite breccia complex	9.0	1
Volcanic	8.0	2
Quartz-pebble conglomerates	1.8	1
Vein	1.6	6
Intrusive	<1	3
Surficial	0	-
Collapse breccia	0	-
Phosphorite	0	-
Others	0	-
Total	98.5	40

Geological Setting

Nigeria, geologically lies within the mobile belt affected by the Pan-African Orogeny sandwiched between the geologically more stable and Older West African and Congo Cratons. The diverse rock types can, in order of decreasing age be subdivided into three major groups: The Basement Complex, the Younger Granites and the Sedimentary Series and with their respective metavolcanic or volcanic rocks (Ogezi, 2006).

The study area is made up of migmatites (oldest) and ante-synkinematic granitoids. U-Pb dating of migmatites and the granitoids (Tobusun, 1983) ranges from 680-520Ma. The post kinematic granitoids has emplaced ages ranging from 620-590Ma. After considerable interval, an episode of magmatic activity ensued and granites accompanied by lavas, intruded into the older granites near Burashika (147 ± 7 Ma and 103 ± 5 Ma). (Popoff et al, 1982 and Baudin, 1986). Accumulation of sediments begun in the upper Cretaceous. The oldest strata are a thick and wide spread series of continental grits, sandstones and clays of the Bima Formation (comprise of three members B1, B2 and B3). Other younger sedimentary rocks are the Dukkul, Pindiga, Jessu, Gongila, Gombe and Keri-Keri Formations (Cater et al, 1963; and Ojo, 1982).

Fig.1. Geologic map of Gubrunde and its environs showing areas of uranium mineralization (After Ige et al, 2000)

Uranium Occurrences

Geologically uranium ores occurs in fourteen (14) geological settings around the globe (IAEA, 2009). In view of this research will be restricted to the ores found in the area of study. Northeastern Nigerian uranium ore deposit occurrences are:

1.Sanstone-hosted Mineralization

Sandstone hosted mineralization is the main occurrence in the sedimentary/volcnosedimentary sequences, structurally controlled mineralization consisting of bright yellow secondary uranium, products in transitional brecciated Bima sandstone(B₂, B₃) within wall rock alteration zones. The mineralization is located at Zona and Dali (fig.1). Zona mineralization is located at the northeastern flank of petasyncline along NNE-SSW trending tectonic

wedge or fault zone and Dali deposit features spotty uranium mineralization in the volcanogenic Bima sandstone, (Dada and Suh 2006; and Ige et al 2000).

About 28.6% of world's uranium productions are sandstone deposit type (table 1). A typical example of such deposits around the globe is Mikoulougou deposit in Gabon with an extend of up to 100m long and 40m wide, contains up to 5100Tu at a grade of 0.15-0.5%U, (IAEA, 2009).

2.Vein-type (Granite related U deposit)

The vein-type mineralization occurs in the ganitoids, the major occurrences are the Gubrunde, Kanawa, Ghumchi, Mika and Monkin-Maza deposits.

Gubrunde uranium minerlization located at the SW fringe of the Gubrunde host, north of Gubrunde village, uranium ore occurs in pockets and dessiminated of meta-autunite sheared zone between rhyolite and granites(fig.1). Kanawa mineralization is at the centre of the Gubrunde horst along shear zones trending N-S. (Ige et al 2000, Funtua, 1997). Ghumchi, Mika and Monkin-Manza deposits are of the central massif at zone of brittle –ductile deformation trending N-S and NW-SE (fig.2), hosting primary and secondary rich veinlets along mylonitic foliation showing in many cases wide spread kaolization and geothide formation.(suh and Dada, 1998; Dada and Suh 2006).

However about 1.6% worlds uranium production is from vein-type deposits. A typical example is the Czech Republic Jachymov mineralization, ore bearing veins account for less than 10% of the total rock volume with a depth of nearly 700m and yields almost 10,000tU at grades from 0.1-1%U. (IAEA, 2009)

(1) Porphyritic Granite (2) Faults/fracture (3) Uranium deposits (4) Rivers (5) Settlement
(6) Foot paths (R) Rose diagram showing three main structural trends: N-S; N130E and N30E-N55E

Fig.2. Geological Map of Mika and Environs showing mineralized area.
(Modified After Suh and Dada, 1998)

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Prospect

The exploration for uranium in northeastern Nigeria peaked between 1976-1983 with the establishment of the Nigeria uranium mining company (NUMCO) in 1978, and has been abandoned for its failure to find an economic deposits. (Arabi et al, 2012 and Mallo, 2012). Further researches now are being carried out by universities research centers.

Radiometric geochemical analysis at Gubrunde and Kanawa shows that elements and isotopes of U, Zn, Cu, P₂O₅, ²²⁶Ra, ²¹⁰Pb, ²³⁴Th or their ratios could in addition to Pb, Ba, Ce can serve as pathfinder elements in search for economic ore deposits (Okujeni et.al 1994 and Ige et.al, 1994). Reports show that concentration of ²²⁶Radon is 1000-2000bq/kg at Kanawa and uranium concentration at Kanawa: 15ppm, Zona: 6.5ppm and highest at Gubrunde: >500ppm (Ige et al 2000 and Funtua, 1997).

Mesotstructures and microstructures evidences at Mika mineralization shows two model (fig. 2), primary deposits trending N-S which is syngenetic and the second is the secondary deposit (epigenetic) in open fractures trending N130E, (Suh and Dada, 1997). Preliminary radiometric studies at Monkin-Manza granitoids of 100-245cps (Haruna et al, 2011). Also an attempt was made to extract kanawa uranium ore by pug-cure leaching, 94.5kg H₂SO₄ per tU and yielded about 96% of uranium, (Ogunleye, 2004).

DISCUSSION

Even in the most experienced and a competent hand, mineral exploration is an expensive, risky and time consuming venture. It has been describe as a mixture of art and science, hence most exploration projects start from general ideas and geological concepts and it involves a great variety of field and laboratory work, ranging from simple visual inspection of the ground to a detailed assessment of the economic feasibility of a prospect.

Uranium exploration is no different from the above, its sole advantage being that uranium can be detected from a far because it emits gamma radiation. Therefore, radiometric techniques are the most useful exploration methods in developing countries.

Uranium exploration in the northeastern Nigeria was conducted by Nigerian uranium mining company (NUMCO) in the eighties, its failure to find economic deposits cannot serve as an excuse by the government to abandoned search for economic uranium deposits. It is associated with the following problems:

1. Lack of, or difficulty in obtaining the requisite number of qualified personnel for field and laboratory studies leads to failure to find economic uranium deposits.
2. Lack of administrative and technological infrastructures needed to support exploration effectively. Almost all the research carried out by the universities research centers, analysis are done in foreign countries and is expensive. In fact there is no record on borehole radiometric logging in mineralized areas.
3. Inadequate fund for the exploration programme, as of now researches are funded by universities research grand which is insufficient for such expensive project.

Fig.3. Uranium Exploration Sequence (Barretto, 1981)

Recommended Strategies

The need for qualified professionals in the mining sector cannot be overemphasized. To execute uranium prospect projects successfully, there is a need for a standard minimum level of professionals that will handle such project to bring a technical report that will convince the government and private investors to have interest in uranium mining. At least right now, there is appreciable increase in number of professionals to handle it unlike in the eighties.

Technological infrastructures needed for exploration has to be improve because there are applicable new techniques for uranium prospecting around the globe. The energy research centers have to be well equipped with facilities and equipments, because right analyses are conducted abroad. There is a need for aerial radiometric surveys, borehole radiometric logging, surface resistivity and induced polarization. The procedures or sequences outlined by Barretto, 1981 (Fig.3), if carried systematically, it will be possible to obtain both an inventory of the geology, and an assessment of the mineral potential of the area with minimum investment and maximum efficiency.

The occurrence of secondary uranium deposits in the Bima sandstone at Zona and Dali, for long been regarded as the potential source for economic deposits, but such assumption is elusive as drilling programs by NUMCO shows abortive. The next option left is to pursue exploration for primary uranium deposits at Gubrunde, Kanawa, Ghumci and Mika with proper understanding of the elemental/isotopes primary dispersion pattern associated with the known occurrence.

Furthermore, one of the major constraints in search for economic deposits is lack of adequate funding. Government should seriously invest in mineral exploration to boost another alternative source of revenue and job creation.

Lastly, for a successful exploration and exploitation prospecting, proper environmental impact assessment has to be evaluated. For example the abandoned mining sites at Gubrunde horst, recent report (Arabi et al, 2012) have shown contamination of groundwater in the settlement areas with radioactive isotopes of 30µg/L, which is a serious problem to the inhabitants.

CONCLUSION

Nigerian GDP in mineral sector is just 0.3% to national economy with enormous mineral deposits in Nigeria. Uranium exploration is no of exception particularly the northeastern Nigeria, in which her potential is well recorded even though there is no record of economic deposits.

The future hold of such economic uranium deposits are the primary deposits of Gubrunde horst, Ghumci and Mika. Borehole radiometric logging has to be carried out, so as to come up with conclusive technical report.

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